

Accelerating T2-map fitting in the brain with a Recurrent Inference Machine

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INTRODUCTION Quantitative MRI requires a time-consuming parameter fitting operation. In this work, we attempt to reduce the fitting time in T2 maps with a model-based recurrent inference machine (RIM). **METHODS** The methodology developed by Sabidussi et al¹ was adapted to a distinct acquisition protocol. Training and validation data were simulated from 10 discrete anatomical models from BrainWeb², split into 40×40 random patches. RIM models were trained and validated with 72000 and 7200 respectively, varying the number of patches in each batch (24, 72, 200), the inclusion of empty patches corresponding to background noise, and simulated noise in the images (standard deviation with a fixed value for all patches or chosen from a standard log-normal distribution), and compared with exponential fitting. Testing data was acquired in vivo with a MSE sequence at 3T with 32 echoes, T2=10:10:320 ms.

RESULTS The optimal training hyperparameters for this protocol were 72 patches per batch, using patches without anatomical information, and acquisition noise with a variable standard deviation across patches. Generating a T2 map with a trained RIM took an average of 0.92 s across 15 experiments, 3.6 times faster than performing exponential fitting.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION T2 maps obtained with the RIM closely resemble the maps obtained by exponential fitting for gray and white matter. Training hyperparameters strongly influence the quality of the maps and may need to be adjusted when applying the RIM to different acquisition protocols.

Figure 1. A) RIM architecture for optimization step j . B) T2 maps obtained with exponential fitting, the RIM with the optimal training hyperparameters (72 patches, including empty patches and acquisition noise with a log-uniform standard deviation), and difference between them. Zoom-in of the same maps with a different scale. C) Relative bias maps for 4 of the models studied, with respect to the exponential fit, varying the number of patches, the inclusion of patches without anatomical information and the acquisition noise of the training images.

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Keywords Magnetic Resonance Imaging — Deep learning — Model-based relaxometry — T2 mapping